

EVALUATION OF DEPRESSION AND SLEEP QUALITY IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING DIALYSIS

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Abstract

Background: When the kidneys stop functioning properly, dialysis is used to eliminate waste and excess fluid from the blood. Hemodialysis is the most widely utilized form of dialysis among all of its variations.

Acute renal injury and diseases that impair your kidneys' capacity to remove waste from your blood are combined to become chronic kidney disease. Wastes can accumulate to dangerously high blood levels and cause sickness if kidney disease gets worse.

Maintaining the body's circadian rhythm depends in large part on sleep. Heart disease, diabetes, depression, falls, accidents, memory loss, and a low quality of life are all linked to lack of sleep. Sleep patterns are compromised by medications taken by older persons and other medical conditions, even though typical aging changes can affect the quality of sleep. Sleep quality and patterns are thoroughly assessed before beginning a nursing examination of sleep.

The prevalent and dangerous medical condition known as depression (major depressive disorder) has a detrimental impact on one's emotions, thoughts, and behavior. Luckily, treatment is available. A decrease in interest in past enjoyable activities and/or depressive moods are symptoms of depression.

Aims and objective: The objective of this study is to analyse the quality of sleep using Pittsburg sleep quality index (PSQI) and depression level of patients using Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) and to determine whether depression and sleep quality are related in dialysis patients.

Methodology: A cross sectional observational study here Depression and sleep are taken into consideration in patients undergoing dialysis.

Results: This study which aims in assessing the quality of sleep among dialysis patients as there is a paucity of literature which measures the co-morbid depression and quality of sleep in dialysis patients. In this study 392 patients were recruited of which 250 (63.8%) were males and 142 (36.2%) were females.

Beck Depression Scale (BDI) consists of 21 questions was used to measure the level of depression in patients. Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) consists of 7 aspects, and validated self-rated questionnaire and used to measure the quality of sleep.

Conclusion: Our study which aims in assessing the quality of sleep among patients undergoing dialysis demonstrated that the quality of sleep reduces significantly with associated depression level of the patients.

Keywords: Dialysis, Hemodialysis, Chronic Kidney Diseases, Depression, Sleep.

Introduction

Humans can live normally with just one kidney as one has more functioning renal tissue than is needed to survive only when the functioning of kidney tissue is greatly diminished does one develop chronic kidney disease⁽¹⁾. Kidney failure is a worldwide public health problem, with increasing incidence and prevalence, high health care costs, and poor outcomes⁽²⁾.

Kidney failure is defined by a glomerular filtration rate $<15 \text{ ml/min/1.73 m}^2$ and may be treated using Kidney replacement therapy (which refers to either dialysis or transplantation) or with supportive care⁽³⁾.

Hemodialysis (HD) is the most prevalent renal replacement therapy for end-stage renal disease (ESRD)⁽⁴⁾. Patients on hemodialysis (HD) commonly suffer from poor sleep quality which in turn compromises their quality of life and well as their mortality risk according to many studies⁽⁵⁾. Some investigators hypothesized that end-stage renal disease (ESRD) directly influences the quality of sleep⁽⁶⁾.

Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) who are treated with dialysis experience many risks to their health-related quality of life (HRQOL), both from the myriad symptoms of ESRD itself and from the psychological and physical strain of receiving dialysis. For these

patients, the careful assessment of HRQOL can help guide the provision of medical management to optimize their health experience⁽⁷⁾.

Sleep problems are a serious public concern because they affect quality of life and well being⁽⁸⁾. In addition, sleep disturbances are common among end-stage renal disease (ESRD) patients that further impair quality of life and increase mortality rates⁽¹⁸⁾. The prevalence of sleep disorders is higher in patients with kidney failure than the general population⁽⁹⁾. Individuals with poor quality of sleep show many physical and cognitive symptoms, such as tiredness, exhaustion, difficulty concentrating, decreased pain threshold, loss of appetite, nervousness, anxiety, and depression⁽¹⁰⁾. The most frequently reported complaints of patients with sleep disorders are insomnia, restless leg syndrome, sleep disordered breathing and excessive daytime sleepiness⁽¹¹⁾.

Across the world, the percentage of elderly people suffering from end-stage renal disease (ESRD) is growing. Compared to the general population, elderly dialysis patients have been reported to be more prone to depression⁽¹²⁾. Sleep disorders are regarded as a risk factor for the recurrence of major depression⁽¹³⁾.

Depression is the main predictor of QOL (Quality of Life)⁽¹⁴⁾. Undiagnosed and untreated depression can reduce quality of life and encourage suicidal attempts in hemodialysis patients. Since sleep is essential to physical and psychological health in all individuals including hemodialysis patients⁽¹⁵⁾. The presence of sleep disorder is associated with lower quality of life and higher mortality in patients on dialysis⁽¹⁶⁾. In order to improve the quality of life for patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD), it is crucial to look into the risk factors linked to sleep problems and enhance the quality of sleep in these individuals. and probably reduce associated mortality⁽¹⁷⁾. Beck Depression Inventory for the assessment of depression and Pittsburgh sleep quality for the assessment of sleep quality⁽¹⁸⁾.

Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI)

An efficient tool for assessing the quantity and quality of sleep that older adults get is the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). Seven categories are measured in order to distinguish between "good" and "poor" sleep: subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, length, habitual sleep efficiency and interruptions, use of sleep medicine, and dysfunction during the previous month's daytime hours. Each of these seven sleep domains is rated by the customer. The responses are graded on a scale from 0 (no difficulty) to 3 (extreme

difficulty). The sum of the individual component scores yields the global score, which ranges from 0 to 21. A high score suggests inadequate sleep.

A sleeper is considered "poor" if their global sum is "5" or above. Even when the client's roommate or bed partner is asked to evaluate them on a few of the questions, neither the associated instrument nor the scoring system account for this information. The University of Pittsburgh Sleep Medicine Institute has further details regarding administration and scoring.

Beck Depression Inventory:

The Beck Depression Inventory (BDI, BDI-1A, BDI-II), originally created by Aaron T. Beck, is a multiple-choice, 21-item self-scored test which is one of the most used psychometric assessments for gauging depression severity. People who are thirteen years of age or older can now use the BDI-II. It includes of questions about symptoms of depression, like sadness and irritation, thoughts like guilt or a sense of being punished, in addition to bodily manifestations like exhaustion, weight loss, and a lack of desire for sex. The BDI is available in three versions: the 1978 revision of the original 1961 BDI, known as the BDI-1A, and the 1996 publication of the BDI-II.

A Critical Analysis of the Beck Depression Inventory

Once you have finished answering the questions, count the numbers to the right of each marked question to find the total score for each of the twenty-one questions. Sixty-three would be the maximum possible score for the entire exam. On all twenty-one questions, this would indicate that you circled number three. The test might have the lowest possible score of zero because there is no possible score lower than zero for each question. This implies that you would circle 0 for every question. The table below can be used to assess your depression.

Overall Rating in Depression Scales

- 1–10 _____ These fluctuations are accepted as typical.
- 11-16 _____ Slight disruption of mood
- 17–20 _____ Clinically borderline depressive
- 21 – 30 _____ Depression in the middle range
- 32–40 _____ Severe depressive illness
- Above 40 _____ Exceptional

Materials and methods:

It is a cross-sectional observational study and 392 patients were involved in the study. Depression was assessed using Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) which consists of 21 self-rated questionnaire to measure the level of depression in patients and the quality of sleep in our study was assessed using Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), PSQI is a validated self-rated questionnaire that assesses sleep problems in seven aspects including habitual quality of sleep, duration of sleep latency, use of sleep drugs, and dysfunction during the day. Dialysis people are undergoing depression and sleep quality change.

Inclusion Criteria: Patient undergoing dialysis

Exclusion Criteria: Patient who are already diagnosed with Psychiatric disorders

Results:

Distribution of Gender

Gender	No of Patients
Male	250
Female	142

Table I: Gender wise distribution of patients

Figure 1: Gender distribution

- The above graph depicts the information about the involvement of male and female dialysis patients involved in study.
- In overall, patients males were more than the females.
- In detail out of 392 patients (100%), females were n=142(36.2%) & males were n=250 (63.8%)

Depression Classification by using BDI Scale

Depression Classification	Number of Patients
Normal	12
Mild Moderate	29
Borderline	36
Moderate	82
Severe	75
Extreme	16

Table II: Indicates the data of male patients with depression classification by using BDI Scale

Figure2:Shows levels of depression in male

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with depression in males.
- Beck Depression Scale (BDI) which consists of 21 questions was used to measure the level of depression in 250 males patients, depression is classified as normal 12 (4.8%), mild moderate 29 (11.6%), Borderline 36 (14.4), Moderate 82 (32.8%), Severe depression 75 (30%), and Extreme depression 16 (6.4%).

Depression classification by using BDI scale in Female

Depression Classification	Number of Patients
Normal	09
Mild Moderate	26
Borderline	31
Moderate	54
Severe	18
Extreme	04

Table III: Indicates the data of female patients with depression classification by using PSQI Scale

Figure3: Shows the levels of depression in female by using BDI scale

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with depression in females.
- Beck Depression Scale (BDI) which consists of 21 questions was used to measure the level of depression in 142 females patients, depression is classified as normal 09 (6.3%), mild moderate 26 (18.3%), Borderline 31(21.9%), Moderate 54 (38%), Severe depression 18 (12.7%), and Extreme depression 4 (2.8%).

Sleep patterns in male by using PSQI Scale

Sleep Pattern	Number of Patients
Very Good	45
Fairly Good	95
Fairly Bad	91
Very Bad	19

Table IV: Indicates sleep pattern in male by using PSQI Scale

Figure 4: Shows the levels of sleep patterns in male by using PSQI

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with sleep quality in males
- The quality of sleep in this study was assessed by using Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). PSQI is validated self-rated questionnaire that assesses sleep problems in seven aspects including sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleep medications and daytime dysfunction.
- Among the males patients sleep patterns observed are very good 45 (18%), fairly good 95 (38%), fairly bad 91 (36.4%), very bad 19 (7.6%)

Sleep Patterns in females by using PSQI

Sleep Pattern	Number of Patients
Very Good	18
Fairly Good	55
Fairly Bad	58
Very Bad	11

Table V: Indicates sleep patterns in females by using PSQI

Graph 5: Shows the levels of sleep patterns in female by using PSQI

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with sleep quality in females
- The quality of sleep in this study was assessed by using Pittsburg Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). PSQI is validated self-rated questionnaire that assesses sleep problems in seven aspects including sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleep medications and daytime dysfunction.
- Among the females patients sleep patterns observed are very good 18 (12.6%), fairly good 55 (40.8%), fairly bad 58 (38.8%), very bad 11 (7.8%)

Good Sleep or Poor Sleep patterns in male patients by using PSQI scale

Sleep Patterns	Number of Patients
Good Sleep	57
Poor Sleep	193

Table VI: Indicates good sleep or poor sleep patterns in male patients by using PSQI scale

Graph 6: Shows the level of good sleep or poor sleep patterns in male patients by using PSQI scale

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with good or poor sleep patterns in males
- A global sum of “5” or greater indicates a “poor” sleeper in the PSQI scale
- The total number of males patients are 250 (100%) where poor sleeper n =193 (77.2%) & good sleeper n = 57 (22.8%)

Good Sleep or Poor Sleep patterns in female patients by using PSQI scale

Sleep Patterns	Number of Patients
Good Sleep	41
Poor Sleep	101

Table VII: Indicates good sleep or poor sleep patterns in female patients by using PSQI scale

Graph 7: Shows the level of good sleep or poor sleep patterns in female patients by using PSQI scale

- The above bar graph depicts the information about the percentage of patients with good or poor sleep patterns in females
- A global sum of “5” or greater indicates a “poor” sleeper in the PSQI scale
- The total number of males patients are 142 (100%) where poor sleeper n = 101 (71.2%) & good sleeper n = 41 (28.8%)

Discussion:

The study was carried out in Hanamkonda in Vishwas Super Speciality Hospital and Dialysis Centre. The primary aim of the research is to raise awareness and provide guidance to the dialysis patients groups. Worldwide, more than 2 million people undergo dialysis treatment as a part of their ESRD treatment. So the people undergoing dialysis treatments are suffering with sleep disturbances and depression.

We performed the study to evaluate depression and sleep disturbances in dialysis patients; both conditions were common. Therefore, it is essential that medical professionals understand the various facets of low quality of life in dialysis patients. Further, more, additional research is required to evaluate the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions in these patients as well as to elucidate the risk factors for depression and sleep disturbances⁽⁷⁾.

Disturbed sleep is among the cardinal symptoms of major depression; infact, it has been estimated that 90% of patients with depression complain about sleep quality. On the otherhand, bothpoorsleep, and depression in Hemodialysis patients (HP) have been associated with reduced QoL and increased mortality risk. Incorporating a standard assessment and eventually treatment of depressive symptoms into the care provided to haemodialysis patients might improve psychological well-being, insomnia and quality of life, and, consequently, reduce mortality risk in this population⁽¹⁹⁾.

The poor sleepers had higher BDI scores and a higher ratio of females comparing to the good sleepers compared to this our study shows that higher poor sleepers are females⁽²⁰⁾.

Conclusion:

Our study which aimed in assessing quality of sleep and depression among patients undergoing dialysis and correlation between sleep and depression in patients undergoing dialysis demonstrated that quality of sleep reduces significantly along with depression. Patients of age below 55 years were suffering from CKD majorly, and if the GFR rate is below 15 it leads to kidney failure and patient will be on dialysis or kidney transplantation. The main purpose of the study is to create awareness on dialysis and improve the quality of life in patients if disease is diagnosed in early stages. Finally our study is conducted in hanamkonda, can help the society and reduce the chances of CKD

which leads to dialysis. Further researches must be conducted in order to analyse the relationship between dialysis, depression and sleep

Data Availability:

All the data collected during the study are presented in this manuscript, and no data from the study have been or will be published separately. We attest that we will provide the data if requested according to the policy.

Consent:

All participants signed informed consent before their participation.

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Conflict Of Interest:

All authors declare that this article content has no conflict of interest.

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